

ARCHITECTURE

JUSTIFICATION OF RATIONAL METHODS OF INSTALLATION OF PVC WINDOW STRUCTURES

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Abstract

Rational methods for the installation of polyvinyl chloride (hereinafter referred to as PVC) window structures in residential buildings are developed based on the principle of guaranteed comfortable living space (namely, a comfortable microclimate, specific sound insulation, and long-term durability). They also take into account design features and technical conditions; in the case of existing buildings, it is necessary to conduct an assessment of characteristic damages and defects, work conditions, and organizational constraints.

The research and justification of rational methods apply not only to multi-story buildings but also to private housing and, notably, architectural monuments. This is because the replacement or repair of translucent building envelopes must not compromise the integrity of the building's energy-efficient shell and must preserve the building's original appearance. Furthermore, maintaining both a comfortable indoor climate and the building's architectural and historical identity is of paramount importance.

The determination of installation methods and technologies has been addressed in numerous works both in Ukraine and abroad; however, these primarily focus on major structural elements. The selection of installation technologies for PVC translucent structures is carried out by the construction developer and the contractor, based on current regulatory legislation and economic feasibility. [2–4].

Keywords: window systems, installation methods, current trends in application, influencing factors, low-operation installation systems, technology selection, architecture, restoration, historical identity, translucent building envelopes.

The research and justification of rational installation methods for PVC translucent building envelopes are based on the following principle: the installation technology must ensure high-productivity execution of the entire complex of construction and assembly works. Simultaneously, it must guarantee the energy efficiency of the building shell, sound insulation, and the operational durability of the installation joint throughout the building's long-term lifecycle. Furthermore, buildings classified as architectural monuments must be addressed separately, as installation in such structures must comply with specific requirements tailored to this class of buildings [1].

The principle is implemented through sequential research and justifications, consisting of the following stages:

1. The systematization and generalization of construction-technological characteristics and working conditions during installation; and based on these, the establishment of a system of method-forming features that describe the specific installation requirements for residential buildings, the construction-technological characteristics of the window opening, its technical condition, and its nature. Attention must be paid to works performed on architectural monuments, as we

must preserve their architectural and historical identity [7].

2. Research and justification of rational installation methods for window structures based on the identified system of method-forming features, which accounts for installation conditions, the necessity of additional works, as well as technical state specifics and the presence of characteristic types of openings.

3. Research and justification of rational technological solutions and parameters for the installation of window structures within substantiated groups of methods.

Stage One. The justification of the system of method-defining criteria is carried out through a systematic analysis and generalization of construction-technological characteristics. These describe the type, structural design, and technical condition, equipment and technology, the type and nature of the installation, as well as the specifics of the spatial-planning and structural solutions of the residential building and the conditions for performing construction and assembly works [10].

The result of the systematization and generalization of construction-technological characteristics is a scientifically substantiated system of method-defining

criteria, various combinations of which determine a characteristic production-technological situation.

Stage Two. The research and justification of rational installation methods for PVC window structures are conducted based on the identified system of method-defining criteria.

So, the result of the second stage of the research is a scientifically substantiated system of installation methods for residential window structures, the application of which guarantees specific performance characteristics and the reliable operation of the building.

Stage Three. The substantiation of organizational-technological models for installation workflows is carried out using structural analysis methods applied to the identified groups of methods, based on organizational-technological models developed for each set of method groups.

The result of the research is a scientifically substantiated set of rational technological parameters and solutions that establish the structure and sequence of construction processes, technological parameters, interdependencies, and organizational constraints, the application of which ensures the reliable and safe performance of window structures throughout their entire service life.

Based on the systematization and generalization of construction-technological characteristics and working conditions during the installation of window structures, the following can be adopted as method-defining criteria [5]:

A-criterion. Method for the installation or replacement of window structures.

a_1 - mass installation of window structures in new construction;

a_2 - full or partial replacement of window structures in an existing building;

a_3 - fragmentary replacement or repair of window structures in an existing building.

B-criterion. Parameters of the work front [8].

b_1 - spatial parameters of the work front (number of stories, zones, and work sections);

b_2 - technological parameters of the work front (work volumes and labour intensity of processes);

b_3 - time parameters (installation deadlines, intensity, cyclicity module, flow step, and flow rate);

C-criterion. Techniques for performing installation operations [6].

c_1 - installation with joint insulation using sealing tapes (e.g., membranes/tapes);

c_2 - installation with joint insulation using liquid sealants (e.g., liquid membranes or mastics);

c_3 - out-of-plane (bracket-based) installation: VSThermo/blaugelb TrioTherm systems/illbruck;

c_4 - out-of-plane (bracket-based) installation: VEKAFast system.

D-criterion. Technological feasibility of the installation process.

d_1 - availability of a system of specialized mechanization tools and equipment;

d_2 - availability of a system of specialized construction rigging and inventory;

d_3 - low-operation (minimal step) nature of the window structure installation process;

d_4 - labour intensity of preparatory and auxiliary operations.

E-criterion. Technical condition and the presence of previous modernizations and interventions in the existing building.

e_1 - technical condition of the structures and the building as a whole;

e_2 - nature and degree of damage to the wall infill and window structures;

e_3 - presence of previous modernizations and interventions in the existing building.

F-criterion. Types and methods of restoration for architectural monuments, window, and door structures.

f_1 - analytical restoration;

f_2 - synthetic restoration;

f_3 - restoration with adaptation;

f_4 - conservation.

Analytical restoration involves restoring the functional properties of windows without recreating the original aesthetic appearance of the units as a whole or their individual components.

Synthetic restoration aims to reproduce and reinforce window structures using modern PVC window technologies—specifically appropriate window and door systems, installation techniques, and specialized mounting joint configurations.

Restoration with adaptation involves a comprehensive scope of work featuring the complete replacement of windows while preserving an appearance identical to the original; this approach is aimed at improving functional and energy-efficiency properties.

Conservation is directed at the reinforcement and protection of both the building as a whole and the window opening. It involves the application of specialized materials and specific types of PVC profiles.

The formation of rational installation methods is carried out as a decision-synthesis process, consisting of sequential procedures for organizing the initial system of methods using system-forming factors (Fig. 1).

Fig.1 Procedural-logistical scheme for the formation of rational installation methods for PVC translucent structures.

These factors consist of method-defining criteria, which allow for the organization of the initial system of methods into groups intended to realize the primary installation functions (installation, replacement, or repair). These, in turn, are subdivided into subgroups of methods that reveal the essence of the processes and phenomena underlying the transformation of material elements into construction products. Furthermore, these include methods categorized by technological features (such as the use of tapes or sealants, the application of supplementary installation systems, or the use of restoration materials, among others).

During the stages of forming the B-system (method subgroups) and the C, D, E, and F-systems (methods), new structural elements are introduced that possess functional, constructive, and technological substantiation.

As science and technology advance, the structures of the B-system and the C, D, E, and F-systems can be augmented with new, promising elements.

Consequently, the system of installation methods for residential window structures is established as an open, evolving system.

Window installation methods are formed by taking into account all possible combinations of the method-defining criteria – $B = \{b_1, b_2, b_3\}$, $C = \{c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4\}$, $D = \{d_1, d_2, d_3, d_4\}$, $E = \{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$, $F = \{f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4\}$ established on the basis of a previously conducted construction-technological analysis of the parameters and installation conditions in residential buildings.

Window installation methods are developed for the previously identified groups of methods, namely: I. Mass installation of new structures; II. Replacement of existing structures; III. Partial replacement or repair of structures.

Within the mass installation of window structures (**Group I**), three distinct methods can be identified: I_a –

vertical (sectional) method; I_b – horizontal (floor-by-floor or tier-by-tier) method; and I_c – mixed method.

The vertical (sectional) installation method involves performing work within separate sections, which can significantly accelerate the overall commissioning deadline of the building.

The horizontal (floor-by-floor or tier-by-tier) method is utilized when performing work across a wide work front [9].

The mixed method is utilized in the combined construction of high-rise buildings featuring stylobate sections.

For the replacement of existing structures (**Group II**), two main subgroups can be identified: – replacement of structures during capital renovation, and – replacement of structures following destruction.

Replacement during capital renovation involves the complete dismantling of existing glazing and the installation of new translucent structures into prepared openings that comply with current legislation.

Replacement following destruction involves the removal of damaged structural remains, the restoration (reinforcement, strengthening) and preparation of the opening, and the installation of new translucent structures [7].

These subgroups involve the application of methods similar to those in the first group, namely: II_a – vertical (sectional) method, II_b – horizontal (floor-by-floor or tier-by-tier) method, and II_c – mixed method.

For partial replacement or repair (**Group III**), two subgroups can be identified: partial replacement of window structures within an individual apartment or a specific area of an apartment, and the repair of existing structures (replacement of the sash, gaskets, hardware, or insulated glass units) or the installation of additional elements (roller shutters, mosquito nets, or external reinforcements).

These subgroups form the following methods: III_a – the discrete method, and III_b – the fragmentary method.

The discrete method is characterized by the replacement of individual structures within an apartment or across a building facade.

The fragmentary method is used when performing repair work within a single structure (for example, replacing a portion of the structure or repairing a specific structural element, such as a sash, etc.).

The conducted research on the development and substantiation of window installation methods has enabled the creation of a classification based on these defining attributes.

Architectural monuments require a more meticulous approach to preserving their identity and occupy a distinct segment of methods with specific subgroups, namely:

- Window Restoration (Group A): A.1. Shape stabilization, A.2. Restoration of physical properties, A.3. Repair and modernization;
- Window Recreation (Group B): B.1. Recreation of the original form, B.2. Recreation of structural integrity;
- Window Replacement (Group C): C.1. Sealing of installation joints, C.2. Full replacement with modern systems;
- Window Reinforcement (Group D): D.1. Reinforcement of load-bearing window elements, D.2. Installation of reinforcing and protective structures.

For each subgroup of methods, specific techniques and the conditions for their application have been established:

A.1. Shape stabilization.

A.1.1. Application of reinforcing materials to strengthen load-bearing window elements. Provides reinforcement for statically loaded window components (mullions/transoms) using surface-mounted reinforcing profiles.

A.1.2. Application of fastening and/or reinforcing elements for individual window parts. Ensures the stabilization of the frame and sash geometric dimensions by installing metal corner brackets, plates, and rails to reinforce window components.

A.2. Restoration of Physical Properties.

A.2.1. Repair of cracks and joints in structural elements. Involves the remediation of cracks in the corners of PVC windows and doors using specialized repair materials for sealing and extending the service life of the structure.

A.3. Repair and Modernization.

A.3.1. Application of a renovation (replacement) frame. Utilized for installing a new PVC window when the removal of the old wooden frame is impossible due to the risk of damaging the masonry opening.

A.3.2. Repair of load-bearing window elements. Applied when a window mullion requires replacement (due to deformation, failure, etc.) to restore the structural load-bearing capacity.

A.3.3. Hardware replacement. Intended for cases involving the loss of functional properties of individual hardware components, or for window modernization without full replacement.

A.3.4. Glass unit replacement. Used to improve

the overall energy efficiency of the window by replacing the glass unit with one utilizing low-emissivity (Low-E) glass.

A.3.5. Seal/Gasket replacement. This method is applied in cases of damage or degradation to restore essential window performance characteristics (air permeability and water tightness).

B.1. Recreation of Form.

B.1.1. Application of PVC structural elements. This method is applied to existing PVC windows when replacing or modernizing specific components to recreate the original aesthetic appearance.

B.1.2. Application of PVC repair materials. This method is used to repair the decorative surface of the window profile by applying repair lamination films.

B.2. Recreation of Structural Integrity.

B.2.1. Replacement of individual PVC window elements. This method involves replacing the sash, mullion, or decorative profile to restore structural integrity.

C. 1. Sealing of Installation Joints.

C.1.1. Application of hydro-/vapor-insulation materials. This method involves sealing the window junctions to prevent moisture penetration and subsequent deterioration of the masonry opening using vapor/hydro-insulation tapes or liquid membranes.

C.2. Full Replacement with Modern Systems.

C.1.1. Window replacement with a new PVC unit.

This method is used when it is impossible to repair, restore, or recreate the form and external appearance of the window.

D.1. Reinforcement of Load-bearing Window Elements.

D.1.1. Application of fasteners, anchors, chemical anchors, etc. This method involves reinforcing the window's fixation depending on the condition of the masonry opening, the wall material, etc.

D.1.2. Application of external surface-mounted reinforcing elements. This involves the use of surface-mounted reinforcing components for the mullions of an existing PVC window.

D.2. Installation of Reinforcing and Protective Structures.

D.2.1. Application of a renovation frame. This method involves installing a new PVC window using a renovation frame while retaining the existing frame within the opening.

D.2.2. Application of a renovation frame. This method involves installing a new PVC window using a renovation frame while retaining the existing frame within the opening.

Summary

The obtained results of the classification of methods allow us to draw certain conclusions regarding the areas of application.

Installation methods with seam sealing using tapes or liquid sealants are more often used at mass construction sites of multi-storey buildings, work on sealing installation seams can be performed by both installation teams of window construction contractors and contractors performing facade work.

To obtain higher energy efficiency indicators of the building, we can use methods using remote installation systems. Currently, the market of developers and

suppliers of remote systems is limited to four companies: three companies manufacture a remote installation system from high-density and plastic polystyrene foam (VSThermo, blaugelb Triotherm, illbruck), and one company provides the market with a remote installation system from PVC (VEKAFast). In addition, for work in architectural monuments, the system developer of PVC window systems provides the opportunity to use appropriate profiles for restoration.

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